

LOWLAND TAPIR
CONSERVATION INITIATIVE

**PROTOCOL FOR AGE ESTIMATION
OF LOWLAND TAPIRS (*Tapirus terrestris*)
BASED ON TEETH WEAR AND ERUPTION**

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LTCI - IPÊ
2022

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Introduction

This protocol was developed to support field researchers to accurately estimate the age of wild tapirs by evaluating their dentition. The great majority of the images used in this protocol were recorded by the Lowland Tapir Conservation Initiative (LTCI-IPÊ) over the past 26 years during field expeditions to the Atlantic Forest, Pantanal, Cerrado and Amazon. The photos were taken from both living tapirs captured for the installation of telemetry collars and collection of biological samples and from carcasses of tapirs killed during vehicle collisions in highways (roadkill).

The age estimation is based on specific aspects of the natural processes of teeth eruption and wear. Thus, researchers should consider the individual variation and the potential factors that may influence dental structures throughout the life of a tapir, such as individual feeding habits, diet, teeth crown morphology, presence of lesions, and suboptimal occlusion.

As most mammals, tapirs are diphyodonts, meaning they have two successive sets of teeth during their lifetime – the deciduous set ("baby teeth") and the permanent set. Tapirs are also considered heterodonts due to their different teeth shapes (incisors, canines, premolars and molars), which have evolved to perform distinct functions.

Dentition features can be used to separate tapirs into the following age classes:

The permanent dentition can vary among individuals, but, in general, an adult tapir has 42 permanent teeth with the following dental formula: $2X (I3/3, C1/1, P4/3, M3/3) = 42$ (KUEHN, 1986). The deciduous dental formula is $2X (I3/3, C1/1, P4/3) = 30$. This formula represents the quantity of each type of teeth in half of the cranium, where the type of teeth is indicated by the capital letters (INCISORS, CANINES, PREMOLARS and MOLARS). The numbers are presented as fractions, specifying the quantity of teeth in the upper (or maxillary) and lower (or mandibular) dental arches, respectively.

Therefore, there are three incisors, one canine, four premolars and three molars in one half of the upper dental arch, while the mandibular half has one less premolar. Similarly to horses, the tapir canine and premolars are separated by a diastema. Both the third upper incisor and the lower canine are very well developed, while the upper canine is small.

Figure 1. Dental Arch

Source: MOYANO & GIANNINI, 2017.

CALF

00-11 MONTHS OLD

It is not yet known at which month of age the deciduous teeth start to erupt, but the current literature suggests that the fourth upper premolar is the last deciduous teeth to erupt and may be still erupting by the end of this age class.

8 MONTHS

White deciduous teeth, wide and small.

8 MONTHS

Little developed lower canine, almost the same height as the lower incisors (**ARROW**).

10 MONTHS

Deciduous premolars, without any indication of wear.

11 MONTHS

The lower deciduous canine is a little more developed by the end of this age class, when the calf is approximately 12 months old.

JUVENILE

12-17 MONTHS OLD

All teeth are still deciduous, and the incisors start to wear. The lower canines are more developed and have a darkened region close to the gum, marked by the exposure of the cementum (protection of the tooth root). This dark region becomes more visible until the exchange of the deciduous teeth, typically in 2-year-old tapirs. The upper deciduous canines may be present.

12 MONTHS

1 YEAR

The lower deciduous canine is higher than the lower incisors and has a darkened region close to the gum (**ARROW**). The upper deciduous canine is present.

15 MONTHS

1 YEAR AND 3 MONTHS

Lower deciduous canine with a larger area of cementum exposure (**ARROW**).

16 MONTHS

1 YEAR AND 4 MONTHS

Deciduous incisors at the same height, showing clear signs of wear.

16 MONTHS

1 YEAR AND 4 MONTHS

Deciduous premolars (upper and lower) completely erupted, with well-defined cusps (raised points on the crowns of teeth).

SUB-ADULT

18-23 MONTHS OLD

The wear and dark stains in the deciduous teeth enamel becomes evident. The first molars start to erupt. These are permanent teeth; DECIDUOUS MOLARS DO NOT EXIST.

22 MONTHS

1 YEAR AND 10 MONTHS

Wearing of the deciduous incisors. Lower deciduous canine completely erupted and with evident exposure of the cementum.

22 MONTHS

1 YEAR AND 10 MONTHS

Deciduous premolars with worn cusps and dark stains.

23 MONTHS

1 YEAR AND 11 MONTHS

All deciduous premolars completely erupted and first molar erupting (**ARROW**).

23 MONTHS

1 YEAR AND 11 MONTHS

First lower molar in the process of eruption (**ARROW**).

SUB-ADULT

24-29 MONTHS OLD

The exchange of deciduous teeth by the permanent teeth starts to happen. As well as in other mammals (e.g., equids) the exchange starts by the first incisors (positioned in the center of the arch). This is followed by the exchange of the second and third incisors. The exchange of the lower canines can happen simultaneously to the exchange of the third upper incisors in some individuals, around the 29th month.

24 MONTHS

2 YEARS

Absence of the first right upper incisor (**ARROW**) at 24 months – the likely age for the beginning of teeth exchange.

26 MONTHS

2 YEARS AND 2 MONTHS

Early stages of eruption of the third upper incisor (**ARROW**). First and second upper incisors are permanent, large, with no wear and completely white.

26 MONTHS

2 YEARS AND 2 MONTHS

Deciduous premolars are stained and with evident cusps wear.

29 MONTHS

2 YEARS AND 5 MONTHS

Third upper incisor and lower canine erupting simultaneously (**ARROWS**).

SUB-ADULT

30-35 MONTHS OLD

The eruption of the upper permanent canines starts. The premolars generally exchange at the beginning of this age class, while the lower canines and the third upper permanent incisors are still erupting. The first molar is erupted, and the second molar may be starting to erupt.

30 MONTHS

2 YEARS AND 6 MONTHS

Upper permanent canine starting to erupt (**ARROW**).

31 MONTHS

2 YEARS AND 7 MONTHS

Permanent canines (upper and lower) at different eruption stages (**ARROWS**).

34 MONTHS

2 YEARS AND 10 MONTHS

Upper permanent premolars without wear, with sharp cusps.

36 MONTHS

3 YEARS

Second upper molar starting the process of eruption (**ARROW**).

SUB-ADULT

36-41 MONTHS OLD

The permanent incisors and canines are erupted, and the lower canines have little wear. The permanent premolars are in the final stages of eruption or have already erupted, with no wear. The fourth upper premolar is the last to be exchanged (observation: a fourth lower premolar do not exist). The eruption of the second molars begins.

36 MONTHS

3 YEARS

Lower canine completely erupted and presenting discrete cusp wear.

37 MONTHS

3 YEARS AND 1 MONTH

Permanent premolars, without any wear and with a few stains.

38 MONTHS

3 YEARS AND 2 MONTHS

Second lower molar still erupting (**ARROW**).

38 MONTHS

3 YEARS AND 2 MONTHS

Fourth upper premolar without any wear (**BLUE ARROW**). Second upper molar in the process of eruption (**RED ARROW**).

SUB-ADULT

42-47 MONTHS OLD

All permanent premolars are completely erupted. The lower canines have evident cusp wear.

42 MONTHS

3 YEARS AND 6 MONTHS

Permanent premolars with well-defined cusps.

46 MONTHS

3 YEARS AND 10 MONTHS

Evident wear in the cusp of the lower canine.

ADULT

4 YEARS OLD

The incisors still have pointy cusps. The lower canines have more evident signs of wear, starting to have dentin exposure (the inner layer of teeth, which has an orange appearance). The cusps of the premolars start to become rounded due to teeth wear. The upper canines and the second molars are completely erupted.

4 YEARS

Lower canines with more evident cusp wear, and with dentin exposure (the light orange part - **ARROW**).

4 YEARS

Upper canine completely developed and incisors without wear.

4 YEARS

Permanent premolars completely erupted.

4 YEARS

Permanent premolars with lightly worn cusps.

ADULT

5 YEARS OLD

The incisors cusps become less sharp due to wear. It is possible to observe a more intense wear in the lower canines and premolars, with dentin exposure in some teeth. The first molar starts to become concave, and the third molar may start to erupt.

5 YEARS

Lower canine is more eroded.

5 YEARS

Lower incisors with more worn and flat cusps.

5 YEARS

Premolars with visible wear and roundish cusps.

5 YEARS

Third molar starting to erupt (**ARROW**) and first molar starting to show signs of wear.

ADULT

6 YEARS OLD

The process of teeth erosion continues to advance, and it is now possible to observe the flatness of the lingual surface (internal) in the lower canines. The first upper premolars are concave, but still have well-defined cusps.

6 YEARS

Lateral view of inferior canine erosion.

6 YEARS

Lower canine with flat lingual surface, showing a high level of erosion.

6 YEARS

Premolar erosion, starting to become concave.

6 YEARS

Worn lower premolars, but still with defined cusps.

ADULT

7 YEARS OLD

Intense erosion in the lower canines, but it is NOT YET POSSIBLE to observe the dental star. All teeth are completely erupted, including the third molars. The second upper molars start to become concave.

7 YEARS

The erosion in the lower canine is very evident, but with no apparent dental star.

7 YEARS

Visible erosion in the incisors and lower canines.

7 YEARS

Premolars become less pointy, with significant erosion and concave shape.

7 YEARS

Upper premolars are concave and have rounded cusps.

ADULT

8 YEARS OLD

A dental star (dark spot) is observable in the lower canines due to the intense erosion. The incisors are worn and have exposed dentin, but the dental star is not yet apparent.

8 YEARS

Well-defined dental star in the lower canines (**ARROW**).

8 YEARS

Worn incisors with dentin exposure, but no dental star.

8 YEARS

Upper premolars with dentin exposure, eroded, concave and with poorly defined cusps.

8 YEARS

Eroded third upper molar, with potential dentin exposure in the cusps.

ADULT

9 YEARS OLD

The incisors start to show the dental star. The cusps of the lower canines start to become flat. With the exception of the third molar, all upper premolars and molars are concave.

9 YEARS

Visible dental star in the incisors (**ARROW**).

9 YEARS

Lower canine eroded and without its original pointy tip.

9 YEARS

Dental star apparent in the lower canines and third incisor.

9 YEARS

Concave premolars, very eroded.

ADULT

10 YEARS OLD

The teeth start to develop a darker yellow appearance. The incisors become rounded and have an overall similar height due to the advanced erosion process, with the exception of the third upper incisor, which is still higher than the others. The dental stars of the lower canines increase in size. The premolars and molars have blunt cusps, but the third molar still have some well-defined cusps.

10 YEARS

Teeth with darkened yellow appearance and rounded incisors.

10 YEARS

Large dental star in the lower canines. Highly eroded incisors.

10 YEARS

Premolars and molars with evident erosion, rounded cusps and concave.

10 YEARS

Third molar eroded but with well-defined cusps (**ARROW**).

ADULT

11-12 YEARS OLD

In between 11 and 12 years of age, the third upper incisors start to show wear signs. The shape of the lower canines become increasingly triangular due to the lingual surface erosion. Both lower canines and incisors still have dental stars. All premolars and molars are concave, and many individuals have dental calculus (tartar).

11 YEARS

Highly eroded lower canine, with a triangular shape.

11 YEARS

Intense erosion in the upper and lower premolars.

12 YEARS

Evident erosion in the third upper incisor. The dental star is still apparent in the lower canines and incisors.

12 YEARS

Accumulation of tartar in the premolars, particularly in the areas close to the gum.

ADULT

13-14 YEARS OLD

All individuals have dental calculus, particularly in the premolars. Lower canines are intensely eroded and have a triangular shape.

14 YEARS

Significant wear on all incisors and lower canines.

14 YEARS

Lower canine with pronounced triangular shape.

14 YEARS

Very eroded lower canine.

14 YEARS

Eroded premolars with accumulation of calcified dental calculus.

ADULT

15-16 YEARS OLD

Intense erosion observed in all teeth, including the third molar. The incisors may be in the same height. The lower canines lack well-defined cusps (the tip of the canines becomes rounded).

15 YEARS

Very eroded incisors, most with the same height. Lower canine with rounded cusp.

15 YEARS

Very eroded premolars, with dentin exposure and an almost flat surface.

16 YEARS

Large accumulation of dental calculus in the premolars.

16 YEARS

Intense erosion of the premolars and molars, which are concave and have dentin exposure.

ADULT

17-19 YEARS OLD

The erosion in the upper canines becomes evident, as their pointy tips are lost. The third upper incisors may reach the same height of the other incisors. The lower canines can also be at the same height as the lower incisors.

17 YEARS

Erosion in the third upper incisor, which has the same height as the first and second upper incisors.

19 YEARS

Lower canine with the same height as the lower incisors.

19 YEARS

Upper canine starting to show signs of erosion, with cusp loss.

19 YEARS

Premolars with intense erosion, at the same height as some parts of the gum.

ADULT-OLD

OLDER THAN 20 YEARS

At this age class, both canines and incisors have such high level of erosion that, in general, no longer present dental stars. If present, the dental stars are smaller and less dark. Some individuals may have missing teeth (generally incisors and canines). The premolars are at the same height as the gum.

20 YEARS

Dental stars are no longer visible in the lower incisors and canines.

20 YEARS

Intense erosion in the incisors and canines.

20 YEARS

All premolars and molars are eroded and have dentin exposure.

21 YEARS

Missing upper incisors.

AGE-RELATED TAPIR DENTAL ANATOMY

Table 1. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

2 YEARS OLD

Incisor	Deciduous; Incisors may be absent (beginning of the teeth exchange).
Upper Canine	Deciduous; Exchange at approximately 30-31 months.
Lower Canine	Deciduous; Exchange at approximately 29 months.
Premolar 1	Deciduous; Exchange sometime in between 24 and 36 months.
Premolar 2	Deciduous; Exchange sometime in between 24 and 36 months.
Premolar 3	Deciduous.
Premolar 4	Deciduous.
Molar 1	Little to no wear.
Molar 2	Absent.
Molar 3	Absent.

Table 2. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

3 YEARS OLD

Incisor	Permanent, no wear.
Upper Canine	Permanent, completely erupted or at the final stages of eruption.
Lower Canine	Permanent, completely erupted.
Premolar 1	Little or no wear.
Premolar 2	Little or no wear.
Premolar 3	Deciduous being exchanged by the permanent.
Premolar 4	Deciduous being exchanged by the permanent.
Molar 1	Little or no wear.
Molar 2	At the final stages of eruption, no wear.
Molar 3	Absent.

Table 3. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

4 YEARS OLD

Incisor	No wear.
Upper Canine	No wear.
Lower Canine	Little wear, starting to show the dentin.
Premolar 1	Little or no wear.
Premolar 2	Little or no wear.
Premolar 3	Little or no wear.
Premolar 4	Little or no wear (exchange happens before 48 months).
Molar 1	Little or no wear.
Molar 2	Little or no wear.
Molar 3	Absent.

Table 4. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

5 YEARS OLD

Incisor	Little wear.
Upper Canine	No wear.
Lower Canine	Marked erosion signs, with dentin exposure.
Premolar 1	Erosion visible, rounded cusps.
Premolar 2	Erosion visible, rounded cusps.
Premolar 3	Little wear.
Premolar 4	Little wear.
Molar 1	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.
Molar 2	Little or no wear.
Molar 3	Erupts at this age.

Table 5. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

6 YEARS OLD

Incisor	Little wear.
Upper Canine	No wear.
Lower Canine	Erosion evident in the tip, lingual surface flattened.
Premolar 1	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.
Premolar 2	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.
Premolar 3	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.
Premolar 4	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.
Molar 1	Moderate wear, blunt cusps (poorly defined tips).
Molar 2	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.
Molar 3	Little or no wear.

Table 6. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

7 YEARS OLD

Incisor	Moderate wear.
Upper Canine	Little or no wear.
Lower Canine	Moderate erosion.
Premolar 1	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 2	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 3	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.
Premolar 4	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.
Molar 1	Moderate wear, blunt cusps (poorly defined tips).
Molar 2	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.
Molar 3	Little or no wear.

Table 7. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

8 YEARS OLD

Incisor	Moderate wear.
Upper Canine	Little or no wear
Lower Canine	Moderate erosion with visible dental star.
Premolar 1	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 2	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 3	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 4	Concave, intense erosion.
Molar 1	Moderate wear, blunt cusps (poorly defined tips).
Molar 2	Moderate wear, blunt cusps (poorly defined tips).
Molar 3	Little or no wear.

Table 8. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

9 YEARS OLD

Incisor	Moderate erosion with visible dental star.
Upper Canine	Little or no wear.
Lower Canine	Moderate erosion, visible dental star, and cusp becoming rounded.
Premolar 1	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 2	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 3	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 4	Concave, intense erosion.
Molar 1	Concave, intense erosion.
Molar 2	Moderate wear, blunt cusps (poorly defined tips).
Molar 3	Moderate wear with a little of the dentin exposed.

Table 9. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

10 YEARS OLD

Incisor	Intense erosion, visible dental star, and rounded shape.
Upper Canine	Little or no wear.
Lower Canine	Advanced erosion, with large dental star.
Premolar 1	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 2	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 3	Concave, intense erosion.
Premolar 4	Concave, intense erosion.
Molar 1	Concave, intense erosion.
Molar 2	Concave, intense erosion.
Molar 3	Moderate erosion with dentin exposure.

Table 10. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

11-12 YEARS OLD

Incisor	Intense erosion, visible dental star, and rounded shape.
Upper Canine	Little or no wear.
Lower Canine	Advanced erosion, pronounced triangular shape, dental star still visible.
Premolar 1	Concave, extreme erosion.
Premolar 2	Concave, extreme erosion.
Premolar 3	Concave, extreme erosion.
Premolar 4	Concave, extreme erosion.
Molar 1	Concave, extreme erosion.
Molar 2	Concave, extreme erosion.
Molar 3	Moderate erosion, blunt cusps (poorly defined tips).

Table 11. Age-related tapir dental anatomy.

13 YEARS OLD OR OLDER	
Incisor	Advanced erosion, almost all have the same height. At 20 years of age, the dental star may no longer be visible.
Upper Canine	Erosion signs become visible after 16 years of age.
Lower Canine	Extreme erosion, reaching the same height as the lower incisors. Dental star fades.
Premolar 1	Concave, extreme erosion.
Premolar 2	Concave, extreme erosion.
Premolar 3	Concave, extreme erosion.
Premolar 4	Concave, extreme erosion.
Molar 1	Most of the teeth is concave, extreme erosion.
Molar 2	Most of the teeth is concave, extreme erosion.
Molar 3	Concave, extreme erosion.

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